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**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
XALQARO JURNALI**

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XURSHID DAVRON SHE'RIYATIDA ANTITEZA VA METAFORA HODISASINING TILSHUNOSLIKDAGI AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Badiiy asarda ijodkor o'z individual qarashlarini ochib berish uchun turli xil o'xshatishlar, til unsurlaridan foydalanadi. Shoir Xurshid Davron ijodini o'rganar ekanmiz, xalqona ruh bilan birga tarixiylik yetakchi o'rinni egallaganining guvohi bo'lamiz. Shoir bu tarixiy, ijtimoiy, milliy qarashlarini ifodalash uchun ko'pgina til unsurlaridan foydalangan. Shuning uchun ham uning leksikasi boy va rang-barangdir. Uning ijodi orqali til va adabiyotning uzviy aloqasi ham tahlil etiladi. Shoir she'riyatida kamdan-kam uchraydigan tosh ko'zyoshi, oydin qayg'u, soqov bo'ron, mahzun quvonch, qulfsiz kishan kabi oksyumoronlarda tabiat va jamiyatdagi narsa va hodisalarning mohiyati, insonlarning xarakteri ularni bir-biriga taqqoslash, zidlash orqali oydinlashadi. Maqolamizda she'riy matnlarda uchraydigan metafora, antiteza, oksyumoron, takror kabi til hodisalari yordamida inson ruhiyatidagi emotsionallikni ochib berishga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Antiteza, metafora, poetika, Aristotel, lingvopoetika, tasviriylik, she'r.

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THE PHENOMENON OF ANTITHESIS AND METAPHOR IN KHURSHID DAVRON'S POETRY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN LINGUISTICS

ABSTRACT

Within the realm of artistic creation, the author employs a diverse range of comparisons and linguistic elements as a means to articulate their unique perspectives. Through an examination of the works of poet Khurshid Davron, it becomes evident that historical context, alongside national ethos, assumes a central position. The poet adeptly employs various linguistic elements to convey their historical, social, and national convictions, thereby enriching their lexicon with a tapestry of nuance and diversity. Moreover, the interplay between language and literature is intricately woven throughout their oeuvre. The poet's verses lucidly elucidate the presence of rare poetic devices, such as oxymoronic juxtapositions like "stone tears," "clear sadness," "silent storm," and "sad joy," which serve to illuminate the intrinsic essence of natural phenomena, societal events, and the intricacies of human character, by means of comparison and contrast. In this article, particular emphasis is placed upon delving into the emotional intricacies of the human psyche, employing linguistic phenomena such as metaphor, antithesis, oxymoron, and repetition, which manifest themselves within poetic texts.

Keywords: Antithesis, metaphor, poetics, Aristotle, linguopoetics, imagery, poetry.

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ЯЗЫКОВОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ АНТИТЕЗИСА И МЕТАФОРЫ В ПОЭЗИИ ХУРШИД ДАВРАН

АННОТАЦИЯ

В художественном творении автор применяет разнообразные сравнения и языковые элементы для выражения собственных индивидуальных взглядов. Анализируя творчество поэта Хуршида Даврона, мы можем убедиться, что наряду с национальным духом историчность занимает центральное положение. Поэт использовал множество языковых элементов для выражения своих исторических, социальных и национальных убеждений, что придало его лексикону богатство и разнообразие. В его произведениях также осмысливается неотъемлемая взаимосвязь между языком и литературой. В поэзии поэта явственно прослеживаются такие редкие поэтические фигуры речи, как оксюморонические сочетания "каменные слезы", "ясная печаль", "немая буря", "печальная радость", "оковы без замков", которые исследуют сущность явлений и событий в природе, обществе и человеческом характере, сравнивая и контрастируя их друг с другом. В данной статье особое внимание уделяется исследованию эмоциональной составляющей психики человека с использованием таких лингвистических явлений, как метафора, антитеза, оксюморон и повтор, которые обнаруживаются в поэтических текстах.

Ключевые слова: Антитеза, метафора, поэтика, Аристотель, лингвопоэтика, образность, поэзия.

INTRODUCTION. As we read the work of art, we see in the process that literature and language are directly related, that they are like two wings that maintain the balance of a bird. Every element of language in poetry illuminates the pathos of the work, the artistic breath. In particular, let us take the antithesis, which is one of the

stylistic figures of language. Antithesis-rhetorical contradiction is a stylistic figure of contradiction in artistic or oratory speech, consisting of a sharp contrast of concepts, positions, images, situations interconnected with the general structure or internal meaning.

Antithesis, amphithesis, acrothesis, apocope, asyndeton (incoherence), assonance, gradation (climax, anticlimax), diathesis, zeugma, imitation of sound, oxymoron, padistola, paronomasia, polyptoton (polyptote), parallelism, polysendyton (polyptoton) of syntactic figures in scientific literature. , counting, pictorial reference, equality of columns, equality, synoicosis, syllepsis, segmentation, three advantages, diminution, silence, chiasm, ellipsis, inversion are noted, and many of them are actively used in contemporary poetry, including Uzbek poetry.

In the center of our research, we tried to study the following phenomena, which are among the most used tools of artistic representation in fiction, including poetry, that is, syntactic figures:

- a) antithesis;
- b) oxymoron;
- d) acromonogram;
- e) anaphora;
- f) epiphora.

DISCUSSION

"The nature of many things and phenomena in nature and society, the character of human beings, is clarified by comparing, comparing, and contrasting them. Therefore, this comparison is always in step with people in the process of thinking. Such a means of expression is pleasing," says Aristotle in his "Rhetoric" [1.45], because contradictions are easy to understand if they stand side by side. so it is convenient that this means approaching the syllogism by proving, comparing contradictions.

Examples:

All joy to you,
All oppression to me."

Antithesis We find proverbs, sayings, works of art, their names, and their occurrence in poetry, and in our research, we try to express the importance of antithesis in poetry and its role in enhancing, The function of influence. Because, as Professor S. Karimov said: "With the help of antithesis in the artistic style, both the edges of the characters are clearly realized, and the object of expression is revealed in a broader sense." [1.45]

Let's pay attention to the poem "Autumn Tale" by the poet Khurshid Davron: "I showed you to summer it. Although he was cold. We needed autumn." So, given that the antithesis is a phenomenon of contradiction, in the above passage we find only a few words that create an antonym in the text: considered the coldest day of the season. Although it is a bit strange to say that the words summer and winter are antonyms when viewed outside the text, within the text the poet has increased the contradiction of these words and thus the poem's effectiveness. We've come across a lot of antonyms in the summer and winter pairings, but summer and winter have been news to us. The following byte can be quoted without hesitation as one of the newest and most striking contradictions encountered during the poem's analysis:

"I showed you the address,
However, he was on the threshold-

We needed a road." Let us turn our attention to the address word in the passage, which is lexically a place intended for a human to go, and the word threshold is confronted with it in the poem. Because the threshold is the step of the house that is now pressed, it is the specific bridge that enters and exits the house, the threshold is the step

that is now pressed, the position that is chosen, and the address is the goal that is reached and achieved. So, within the text, these two concepts contradict each other and create an antithesis.

Now, let's analyze another contradiction in the same poem:

"I caught you calling it bread.
Hunger is now, however,
But blood was needed. "

In this passage, the words "bread" and "hunger" seem to evoke a contradiction in the text in the form of hunger. Because we know that bread, as a food for human consumption, is a blessing that satisfies the feeling of hunger, and, of course, in its inner sense, it fulfills the concept of satiety. It seems that as this antonym interprets the couple in an incomplete way, we witness the most beautiful contrast between the poet's work in the text. Contradictory notions in the verses should be seen not only as a weapon of rhythmic harmony, but also as a key to unlock the heart, which is further enriched by the following sentences: "I showed you that freedom, They had chains on their hands Let us turn our attention to the words freedom and chain in the passage: Freedom is man, in general, the joy of freedom given to an entire being, and the chain is seen as an object that binds, binds, and deprives freedom. The poet excludes many antonyms in the text, such as freedom and liberty, freedom and condemnation, freedom and imprisonment, and surprises them as well. it is the most effective, defining element of a writer's poetic skill, used in its place and based on logical consistency.

In addition, the poet reveals antonyms even among the groups of words that cause contradictions but are a little difficult to say antonyms, for example:

"I told you this was the last fight,
However, it was the first battle."

When we use the last and the first words in antonyms, we take into account that the first word in the ancient Turkic language means the first, before, and thus we direct the contradictions of the previous and the first to the last word. This, of course, leads to a particularly conflicting significance within the text. As we conclude the poem, we see in the last stanza that the poet presents us with a new contradiction with great talent:

"This is death,
I told you, However,
it was eternal."

Death is the end of human life, and it can be contrasted with words such as life, eternity, life, living, but the poet uses the word eternity, which has the strongest meaning in them. Through this, the antonyms of scientist and eternity are formed.

As we study the linguistic properties of poetic poems, one of the most widely used means of moving meaning in poetic poems is considered a metaphor. The metaphor is the move of the name of one predecessor, taking into account the similarity of one predecessor to another. That is, Metaphor is one of the factors involved in the formation of new meanings of words. We know that the issue of metaphor has been studied and analyzed since ancient times, and research in this area is based on examples in Arastu's "Poetry" He believes that the language of poetry prohibits the use of its own words so that the chosen words, on the one hand, ensure accuracy, on the other hand, differ from everyday speech. Through metaphor, the selfishness of poetry, the interpretation of words, expressions, and events equally capture a person's heart and heart.

RESULTS

We will witness that many elements of our language are used in their place and effectively, and that the reflection of natural phoenicians is celebrated only in a special spirit:

"And the night rain that shrieks,
Dawn hugged mist.
Black field and uplands too,
All of them are well-known to me."

It is noteworthy that in these poems, "Dawn hugged mist" the poet expresses the dawn of dawn and at the same time covering his blue face, thereby describing nightmares that are characteristic of the human spirit, while the surroundings are going on a light but incomprehensible process in the heart. Or in the poem "A Fairy Tale About the Girl and the Wind" he calls the day's night swapping event "the night of the sleeping moon":

"The night of the sleeping moon
It wakes up the smell of your hair."

To express beauty and pleasantness, Acknowledging that the dawn of the night and the setting of the morning in the morning are compared through amazing metaphors, the poet's lyrics also drown in the sea of wonder:

"Hey,... Far from the bird that has strayed,
In the endless fields of my village,
The cotton-picker girls were sleeping
They burying their dreams in the sun."

In this poem, entitled "Autumn Morning" the artist added a tone to the poem by dawning through the image of "burying their dreams in the sun" and the moment when the same sun rose to the tick.

And in the poem "I Became a Tree at Night" the poet painted a picture of the night, likening two different couplet:

"The world slept like a butterfly,
He did not sleep like me in a river."

The butterfly usually lives for a day, and this time is viewed as a process that lasts from early to late. Another reason why the artist introduced this image was that he compared the transition of the day, life, the world, and the equivalent of the time when he blinked and blinked. At the same time, another phenomenon is considered to have described the night as well, through the phrase "the world has slept."

"One of the most important signs of successful likeness is the element of unpredictability, innovation, illustrations" no one objects to the fact that likeness is one of the oldest and most popular language events." [2.5] Indeed, the metaphors in the poet's work ensure that not only for the luxury of words and poetry but also for the meaningful unity in it reaches a person's heart. It is impossible to say that by doing so, the witch created "private metaphors" that were unique and able to reveal his world. In particular, let's take a look at this poem, which revived another night's landscape:

"In my eyes looks sad,
Far from
The night when it flowed."

The poet points out that the state of the night has flowed here, thereby refreshing the time of calm, poetry, and meditation on the human spirit. And in the following poem:

"The nights are the moon in heaven,
The moon is a bathed stream."

Through his metaphor "the moon is a bathed valley" the poet represents the concept of heaven, saying, "The moon is a bathed valley." The moon is a bathed valley, or time in heaven, compared to the state of the night. In one couplet, the poet represents both the heavens and the state of the night. The metaphor can be in many works, which can also be applied by various artists, but creating a combination of forms and content

is considered a separate phenomenon. "If these tools belong only to a separate creative fortress, they will continue to live as a unique example of artistic creativity without spilling out. Therefore, with a broad understanding of the artistic significance of such tools, S. Mamajanov emphasized: "The person facing the illustrations is not a horse that will continue to ride or be saddled. How a poet uses a visual tool depends on the poet's worldview, idea, attitude toward reality, his unique vision, perception, understanding and explanation style, artistic thinking, the characteristics of a lyrical hero, in short, the poet's own style. The real artist never imagines that I should turn to a falon method or a falon visual tool in this place, but rather works on his own thinking, superstition, concept, and prohibition of the material. Just as the spiritual world of the artist and the life that inspires him are like his illustrations"[2.8].

Indeed, in the poet's work, the metaphor was not only a weapon that created silence but also a way of expressing a person's spiritual nightmares through it. As the poet applies the metaphor, we will witness that the thought-out situation is calm, and that evolution in the human spirit represents events through the mushrooms of night and nature.

"The individual metaphors that each writer has his own creative property are the best examples of visual tools, which are also considered a feature of artistic style. In the writer's work, even one metaphorically used word can jiggle an entire text around itself, being considered a sticking point, forming a metaphorical context"[2.20]. Based on the teacher's opinions, professor Suyun Karimov, as we witness a metaphorical picture of natural phenomena in poetic poems, we will determine two things as a result of our study:

1. The poet distinguished natural phenomena, especially the dawn and the setting events of the night, using language elements in a unique way.
2. These natural phenomena indicate that the human life span and the world are transitional, especially the description of the conflict between man and nature, especially the exchange of days and nights.

In the example of the poet's poetry, we have witnessed the phenomenon of antithesis inherent in our language, which is not simple, but has a special significance in the text, proving once again how attractive the Uzbek language is. "A vivid, unique, individual expression of thought, the activity of means of expression, including analogy, metaphor, metonymy, epithets, poetic syntax, synonymy and ambiguity, the multiplicity of images, antithesis, form, simple speech, other functional elements, jargon-dialect. The occurrence of stylistic units, the frequent use of verbs, adjectives, and rhymes, and the fact that all of them serve a great function - figurativeness and emotionality - are these stylistic features"[2.20].

CONCLUSION

The means of expression and image of the language, which serve to fulfill the methodological task in the language of literary literature, are also considered one of the most important signs that determine the position of the artistic style among other functional styles. Because although the need to use language tools in figurative, figurative, and in various forms for figurative images exists to a certain extent in all functional styles of language, but there is no opportunity to use them freely, freely, perfectly and in a wide range as in artistic style. In other styles, mainly known visual means are used, which have become partially stable in the language. And in the artistic text, we come across such manifestations of visual means that can be created only by artistic thinking, which is the product of special creative work.

Indeed, as a stylistic figure, Antithesis gives the sharpest contrast to the opposite, evoking clear images in the mind. Contradiction sharpens the mind, helps to organize

the text or part of it, as a result of which parallel figures, especially antitheses, are used as a means of creating text. Based on the material studied, we found that they use stylistic syntax methods, that is figures, to enliven speech, to give it emotionality, expressiveness, imagery.

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